

A Critical Study on Confucius Philosophy

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Abstract

In China, philosophy has been concerned with every educated person. A philosopher must philosophize; he must think reflectively on life and then express his thoughts systematically. In this research paper we study about Confucius philosophy in the field of ethical and social view in character. From this we conclude that each philosopher has their own standard and Confucius philosophy is centered on the idea of human heartedness.

Key words : Human - heartedness, Righteousness, Ming.

Introduction

Philosophy is systematic reflective thinking on life. In thinking, the thinker is usually conditioned by the surroundings in which he lives. Being in a certain surroundings, he feels life in a certain way, therefore in his philosophy certain emphases which constitute the characteristic of that philosophy. This is true of an individual as it is also true of a people. In this research we shall try to say about Confucius Philosophy in China. When we study Chinese philosophy, we will see the feature of Chinese traditions. Chinese philosophy is chiefly concerned with ethical and social in character. The task of philosophy is to characterize man to become sage. Chinese does not aim to get knowledge for the sake of knowledge. Knowledge is for the sake of cultivating the self. It is not for the search of truth but for the search of good. Confucius philosophy also tend to express his ideas in concrete terms. To express abstract ideas, he uses images which can be directly perceived. The Chinese are also practical in their out - look. In China there are many philosophers, among them we shall attempt to say the philosophy of Confucius.

The Origin of Confucius Philosophy

Confucius (551-479 B.C.) was the father of modern Chinese civilization. The most reliable source of his doctrines is the Analects.

Confucius turned humanism into the strongest driving force in Chinese philosophy. The other major school of Chinese philosophy is Taoism. Taoism and Confucianism are often referred to as opposites. Taoism focuses on the individual life, non-conformity, tranquility, and a transcendental spirit, while Confucianism focuses on social order, conformity, activity, and worldliness. This is to much and extent true. However, the two philosophies work well together, each serving as critiques of the other. It may be better to think of them as two sides of the same coin. It is impossible to understand Chinese philosophy and culture without learning about both Taoism and Confucianism. Taoism is similar to Buddhism except that by following nature, man's nature is fulfilled, not eliminated. In Taoism, a wise leader rules through non-inference with nature. In Confucianism, a wise leader rules through reason, good counsel, and

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respect for the examples set by one's elders and ancestors. In many ways, Taoism and Confucianism set the themes for the continuing struggle between a philosophy of human nature that focuses on spirituality and nature vs. social order and reason.

Confucius and the Six Classics

The rise of the philosophic schools began with the practice of private teaching. So far as modern scholarship can determine, Confucius was the first person in Chinese history thus to teach large numbers of students in a private capacity, by whom he was accompanied during his travels in different states. According to tradition, he had several thousand students, of whom several tens became famous thinkers and scholars. The former number is undoubtedly a gross exaggeration, but there is no question that he was a very influential teacher, and what is more important and unique, China's first private teacher. His ideas are best known through the *Lun Yü* or Confucian Analects, a collection of his scattered sayings which was compiled by some of his disciples.

Confucius was a *ju* and the founder of the *Ju* school, which has been known in the West as the Confucian school. The term *Liu Yi* means the "six arts," i.e., the six liberal arts, but it is more commonly translated as the "Six Classics". These are the *Yi* or Book of Changes, the *Shih* or Book of Odes (or Poetry), the *Shu* or Book of History, the *Li* or Rituals or Rites, the *Yueh* or Music (no longer preserved as a separate work), and the *Ch'un Ch'iu* or Spring and Autumn Annals.

As a matter of fact, however, Confucius was neither the author, commentator, nor even editor of any of the classics. In some respects, to be sure, he was a conservative who upheld tradition. Thus in the rites and music he did try to rectify any deviations from the traditional practices or standards, and instances of so doing are reported in the *Lun Yü* or Analects. Judging from what is said of him in the Analects, however, Confucius never had any intention of writing anything himself for future generations. The writing of books in a private rather than official capacity was an as yet unheard of practice which developed only after the time of Confucius. He was China's first private teacher, but not its first private writer.

The Six Classics had existed before the time of Confucius, and they constituted the cultural legacy of the past. They had been the basis of education for the aristocrats during the early centuries of feudalism of the Chou dynasty. As feudalism began to disintegrate, however, roughly from the seventh century B.C. onward, the tutors of the aristocrats, or even some of the aristocrats themselves—men who had lost their positions and titles but were well versed in the Classics—began to scatter among the people. This class of men was known as the *ju* or literati.

Confucius as an Educator

However, Confucius, was more than a *ju* in the common sense of the word. It is true that in the Analects we find him, from one point of view, being portrayed merely as an educator. He wanted his disciples to be "rounded men" who would be useful to state and society, and therefore he taught them various branches of knowledge based upon the different classics. His primary function as a teacher, he felt, was to interpret to his disciples the ancient cultural heritage. That is why, in his own words as recorded in the Analects, he was "a transmitter and not an origintor". "But this is only one aspect of Confucius, and there is another one as well. This is that, while transmitting the traditional institution and ideas, Confucius gave them interpretations derived from his own moral concepts. "When a man's father is alive, look at the bent of his will. When his father is dead, look at his conduct. If for

three years [of mourning] he does not change from the way of his father, he may be called filial. Confucius stresses the importance of a lengthy mourning period for one's parents - three years is the proper length to mourn for one's father. If a person changes his demeanor as soon as his father has passed away, then it shows how pretentious he had been in the presence of his father. Confucius thinks that we are fully dependent on our parents. For survival and nourishment at least in the first three years of our life; hence, it is only natural that after they depart from us, we should spend three years keeping them in constant regard. This is exemplified in his interpretation of the old custom that on the death of a parent, a son should mourn three years. Confucius commented on this: "The child cannot leave the arms of its parents until it is three years old. This is why the three years' mourning is universally observed throughout the world." In other words, the son was utterly dependent upon his parents for at least the first three years of his life; hence upon their death he should mourn them for an equal length of time in order to express his gratitude. Likewise when teaching the Classics, Confucius gave them new interpretations. Thus in speaking of the Book of Poetry, he stressed its moral value by saying: "In the Book of Poetry there are three hundred poems. But the essence of them can be covered in one sentence: 'Have no depraved thought'." In this way Confucius was more than a mere transmitter, for in transmitting, he originated something new.

This spirit of originating through transmitting was perpetuated by the followers of Confucius, by whom, as the classical texts were handed down from generation to generation, countless commentaries and interpretations were written. Besides the new interpretations which Confucius gave to the classics, he had his own ideas about the individual and society, heaven and man. In regard to society, he held that in order to have a well-ordered one, the most important thing is to carry out what he called the rectification of names. That is, things in actual fact should be made to accord with the implication attached to them by names.

There is an agreement between name and actuality. But if he does not, he is no ruler, even though he may popularly be regarded as such. Every name in the social relationships implies certain responsibilities and duties. Ruler, minister, father and son are all the names of such social relationships, and the individuals bearing these names must fulfill their responsibilities and duties accordingly. Such is the implication of Confucius' theory of the rectification of names.

Human-heartedness and Righteousness

With regard to the virtues of the individual, Confucius emphasized human-heartedness and righteousness, especially the former. Righteousness (yi) means the "oughtness" of a situation. It is a categorical imperative. Every one in society has certain things which he ought to do, and which must be done for their own sake, because they are the morally right things to do. If, however, he does them only because of other non-moral considerations, then even though he does what he ought to do, his action is no longer a righteous one. To use a word often disparaged by Confucius and later Confucianists, he is then acting for "profit." Yi (righteousness) and li (profit) are in Confucianism diametrically opposed terms. Confucius himself says: "The superior man comprehends yi; the small man comprehends li."

The idea of yi is rather formal, but that of jen (human-heartedness) is much more concrete. The formal essence of the duties of man in society is their "oughtness," because all these duties are what he ought to do. But the material essence of these duties is "loving others," i.e., jen or human heartedness. The father acts according to the way a father should act who loves his father. Confucius says: "Human-heartedness consists in loving others." The man who really loves others is one able to perform his duties in society.

Thus the practice of jen consists in consideration for others. “Desiring to sustain oneself, one sustains others; desiring to develop oneself, one develop others.” In other words: “Do to others what you wish yourself.” This is the positive aspect of the practice, which was called by Confucius chung or “conscientiousness to others.” And the negative aspect, which was called by Confucius shu or “altruism.” is : “Do not to do others what you do not wish yourself.” The practice as a whole is called the principle of chung and shu, which is “the way to practice jen.”

This principle was known by some of the later Confucianists as the “principle of applying a measuring square”. That is to say, it is a principle by which one uses oneself as a standard to regulate one’s conduct.

The principle of chung and shu is at the same time the principle of jen, so that the practice of chung and shu means the practice of jen. And this practice leads to the carrying out one’s responsibilities and duties in society, in which is comprised the quality of yi or righteousness.

Knowing Ming

From the idea of righteousness, the Confucianists derived the idea of “doing for nothing.” One does what one ought to do, simply because it is morally right to do it, and not for any consideration external to this moral compulsion.

As we shall see, the Taoists taught the theory of “doing nothing” whereas the Confucianists taught that of “doing for nothing”. A man cannot do nothing, according to Confucianism, because for every man there is something which he ought to do. Nevertheless, what he does is “for nothing,” because the value of doing what he ought to do lies in the doing itself, and not in the external result.

Ming is often translated as Fate, Destiny or Decree. To Confucius, it is meant the Decree of Heaven or Will of Heaven; in other words, it was conceived of as a purposeful force. In later Confucianism, however, Ming simply means the total existent conditions and forces of the whole universe. For the external success of our activity, the cooperation of these conditions is always needed. But this cooperation is wholly beyond our control. Hence the best thing for us to do is simply to try to carry out what we know we ought to carry out, without caring whether in the process we succeed or fail. As a result, we always shall be free from anxiety as to success or fears as to failure, and so shall be happy. This is why Confucius said : “The wise are free from doubts; the virtuous from anxiety; the brave from fear.”

Conclusion

According to Confucius the goal of the philosopher was to become learned, but this concept means more than merely knowing a large number of facts. Rather, on the basis of a board learning in the classic texts, the canon of which he essentially formulated. Confucius’ philosophy emphasize on social and ethical problems. He does not discuss with about the nature. So, Confucius’ philosophy may be interpret humanism. According to Confucius, we need to understand Jen (human-heartedness), Yi (righteousness), Li (ritual) and Chih (wisdom). Confucius held that a person regardless of his or her social status, could become aware of the moral order of the cosmos and his or her proper place in it. Confucius taught the primary of the family and the duties incumbent upon its various members, stressing harmony and unity and the self- evident goodness of the ethical life.

Confucius is not mere conservative. He is also a social reformer. His views are too formalistic. According to him we should do what we ought to do without any consideration for success or failure.

We think that in Confucius philosophy, there are four cardinal values. They are Jen, Yi, Li and Chih. Among them he emphasizes Jen. In Buddha philosophy there are four cardinal values they are Metta, Karuna, Mudita and Uppekha. Among them Metta must be extended to all beings. So Confucius philosophy is seem to be the same of Buddha philosophy.

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